

SUGGESTED STRATEGIES FOR ADULT LEARNERS IN LEARNING NEW WORDS IN SECOND LANGUAGE (ENGLISH)

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Annotation: Vocabulary acquisition process can be different in different age groups owing to a number of reasons, like learners' background knowledge, language level, their ultimate goal, motivation. By taking these factors into consideration, the selection of learning and teaching strategies should be made for adult learners to gain more in less time by turning language users from language learners.

Key words: communication, dictionary, frequency, note-taking, second language acquisition, translation, vocabulary.

Second language acquisition (SLA) possesses high requirements including its grammar, phonology, lexical sources, syntax, discourse as well as vocabulary which is considered as the most essential part of learning. While there are tons of experiments, researches conducted on the sphere of vocabulary, one method, technique or a strategy cannot be stated as a unique effective approach to follow. Because learners' background knowledge, level, learning styles, together with motivation of theirs effect the process of learning and the output. Particularly, in terms of suggesting effective strategies for adult learners in vocabulary learning, their learning trajectory, motivation types as well as ultimate goals should be taken into consideration. Learning and teaching vocabulary has been a popular topic for researchers to explore and analyze. In particular, some of the authors devoted their work for a special group of learners such as age groups, like young learners, adult learners. As many of the authors stated that, teaching adults is far more different than teaching young learners. By investigating their experiments thoroughly contemporary strategies and techniques can be prioritized and adopted for adult

learners, besides, general conclusions can be made according to the selection of strategies. As individualism among adult learners are common, all the investigated strategies cannot be used for a variety of learners, however, the effect of the selected strategy can be evaluated and recommended to use in further researches.

To investigate the most effective way in learning vocabulary Ahmad Azman Mokhtur etl. [6, 35] analyzed seven types of strategies whose usage is more common in adult learners in learning new words of L2. They made a questionnaire among 360 freshmen and sophomore students in Teknoligi University in Perlis. Metacognitive regulation, guessing strategies, dictionary strategies, note-taking strategies, rehearsal strategies, encoding strategies, and activation strategies were experimented among students. Those strategies were divided into several subcategories which clarified the strategies explicitly. According to the results of the research, guessing and dictionary strategies were more preferable for students who were considered as passive strategy users by researchers. With respect to activation strategies more were ignored by students in learning new vocabulary of a target language. Mokhtur mentioned "Activation strategies are the types of strategies which ESL learners use to make interaction with other people so as to discover or practice new words"[6, 38]. According to them, the two mentioned strategies which are preferable for students only help them to find a real meaning of a word, but this is not adequate in language learning. The usage of the word learnt in practice should be taken into account as this is the most crucial stage in language acquisition.

Hatch and Brown [3, 91] claimed that five stages are comprised in vocabulary learning, namely, encountering new words, understanding the word form, realizing the word meaning, merging word form and meaning in memory and utilizing the word in communication. Without the use of vocabulary in communication, learners may become just readers, translators, in short, passive learners of the languages, not users of them. By activation strategies students acquire how to use a language in a real, authentic situations which evaluate learners' relevant and valid knowledge in a language. Another researcher , Paul

Nation [7, 67], tried to demonstrate the effectiveness of linguistic approach including learning a word by dealing with a couple or more aspects of the word, such as its spelling, pronunciation, parts, related derived forms, meaning, collocations, grammar, or restrictions on its usage which are briefly considered as encoding strategies by Mokhtur [6, 37]. By this strategy learners gain theoretical knowledge on the language by being aware of the grammatical and lexical aspects of a word as well. However, this strategy cannot boost the learners to use their gained knowledge in vocabulary in practice being involved in communication. Verdan Dronjic [1, 78] as a researcher illustrated dictionary strategies in a broader sense by analyzing the types of dictionaries, such as monolingual, bilingual and bilingualized dictionaries. Monolingual dictionaries are usually regarded much more effective than the bilingual ones. The reason is that, monolingual dictionaries provide much more detailed and extended information, particularly when the word is used in a sentence with different meanings, contextual meaning together with its synonyms or antonyms.

Moreover, Laufer and Hadar [4, 45] conducted an experiment among Israeli students whose language level are different, namely, multilevel. According to the results, monolingual dictionaries were found as more effective type for each learner whether they are beginner or advanced. Taking the types of dictionaries into consideration, Paul Nation [7, 68] paid attention to other types of vocabulary learning strategies. However, he rejected the usage of memorization which was a subcategory of rehearsal strategies in Mokhtur's research. "Memorization is not a particularly popular way to learn, chiefly because it is seen as boring and uncreative" [7, 70]. What's more, family strategy was supported by Tokowi and Degani [9,121] as a useful way of learning new word in a list of items that are included in a similar type such as fruits, animals or clothes. However, Finchenier and Necol [2, 83] argued that, dealing with new words in a semantic set lead the learners to worsen their memory and language skills.

By studying a number of ways, it can be concluded that, contextual vocabulary learning strategy can increase adult learners' vocabulary range in the

target language. By this strategy, learners not only learn new words, but also, they are forced to use them in practice. Although usage of new vocabulary can be artificial, learners can realize how to use them in context whether in writing or speaking. Especially scientific, political and informative types of passages are preferable to use as a tool to improve vocabulary. No doubt, the choice of the materials depends on the learners' desire as well. Because in contrast with young learners, adults usually have their concrete aims in learning second language, such as having job opportunities, fulfilling educational purposes, making business trips and contracts with foreign countries etc. Thus, vocabulary can be taught thematically as well according to their needs.

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